

Questionnaire

1 Welcome

Welcome!

Your responses to this survey will help us guide the development of future IPSDS courses as well as of the entire program.

Your responses will be kept confidential, will not be shared with the IPSDS faculty on an individual basis, and will have no influence on your grade in any of the IPSDS courses. The results from this survey will only be presented in aggregate form.

This survey is expected to only take approximately 5-10 minutes to complete.

We greatly appreciate your willingness to share your time.

Sincerely,
Zhenya Samoilova
IPSDS Evaluation Officer

2 Page 0 (ID)

Please enter your Evaluation ID:

The ID (3 digits + 3 letters) was sent to you in a separate email message.

3 Page 1

First, we ask some questions about your expectations and choice of the IPSDS program.

4 Page 2

To what extent do you expect to perform better at your work as a result of participating in this program?

- Not at all
- A little
- Somewhat
- A lot
-

5 Page 2.a

What about finding new employment? To what extent do you expect to change your job as a result of the IPSDS?

- Not at all
- A little
- Somewhat
- A lot
-

6 Page 3

How important were the following reasons in choosing to apply for the IPSDS program?

Not at all important A little important Somewhat important Very important

The subject is relevant for my current work

The subject is relevant for my career

development	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The instructors teaching the courses	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The program is administered online	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
The program is tuition-free	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

7 Page 4

Is this your first online course?

we also mean courses not for a grade (e.g. MOOC on Coursera)

- Yes
- No

8.1 Filter for more on online-experience

How much experience do you have with the following elements of online courses?

	No experience	A little experience	Some experience	A lot experience
Pre-recorded lecture videos	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Online-based assessments (e.g. assignments, exams)	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Live online meetings	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Forum discussions	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Peer assessment	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

9 Page 6

Now we are interested to learn about your expectations with respect to your first IPSDS course "Fundamentals of Survey and Data Science."

10 Page 7

On average, how many hours per week do you expect to spend on this course?

hours

11 Page 8

How familiar are you with the subject taught in this course?

- Not at all familiar
- A little familiar
- Somewhat familiar
- Very familiar

12 Page 9

In this part of the survey, we are interested to learn more about you.

13 Page 10 a

According to your work contract, how many hours are you supposed to work a week (in your main job), excluding any paid or unpaid overtime?

hours

14 Page 10

Regardless of your basic or contracted hours, how many hours do you normally work a week (in your main job), including any paid or unpaid overtime?

hours

15 Page 11

How do you feel about opportunities for advancement at your current work?

- Very negative
 - Somewhat negative
 - Neither positive nor negative
 - Somewhat positive
 - Very positive
-

16 Page 11a

To what extent can you decide how your daily work is organized?

- Not at all
 - A little
 - Somewhat
 - A lot
-

17 Page 11 b

To what extent can you decide the time you start and finish work?

- Not at all
 - A little
 - Somewhat
 - A lot
-

18 Page 11 c

To what extent can you choose your pace of work?

- Not at all
 - A little
 - Somewhat
 - A lot
-

19 Page 11 d

Considering efforts and achievements in job, how satisfied are you with your pay?

- Extremely dissatisfied
-
-
-
-
-

-
-
-
-
- Extremely satisfied

20 Page 12

How often does your work involve the following?

	Never	Less than once a month	Once a month	Several times a month	Every week
Working evenings or nights	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Having to work overtime on short notice	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Working at weekends	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>
Working under time pressure	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>	<input type="radio"/>

21 Page 13

All things considered, how satisfied are you with your present job?

- Extremely dissatisfied
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
-
- Extremely satisfied

22 Page 18

Do you currently own a smartphone with internet access?

- Yes
- No

- -
 -
 -
 - A great deal of stress
-

26 Page 17

All things considered, how satisfied are you with your life as a whole nowadays?

- Extremely dissatisfied
 -
 -
 -
 -
 -
 -
 -
 -
 -
 -
 -
 - Extremely satisfied
-

27 Final page

Thank you for your time!
